

Local Government in Moldova

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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with the support of the Congress of Local Authorities of Moldova (CALM)

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Moldova: An Introduction

Viorel Girbu, *Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova, NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Local public administration reform and territorial and administrative reform is a sensitive subject in Moldovan politics. Since the onset of its independence, Moldova saw a major territorial reform implemented in 1998 which proved to be unsuccessful and reversed during the next political cycle with a new political establishment in 2001.

The 1998 territorial and administrative reform brought two important changes. Firstly, the number of second-tier local public administrations (level 2 LPAs) was reduced from 40 *rayons* to ten counties, while the number of first-tier local public administrations (level 1 LPAs) was reduced from 912 to 662 which was later considered insufficient to give a boost for development of LPA level I. Secondly, the functions related to public services were concentrated at the level of the county administration, managed by the Prefect — the representative of the government. The second change was not welcomed by citizens, because it increased the distances between public services and citizens.⁹

The 1998 territorial and administrative reform was basically reverted in 2001, given the new political context in the country. The new regulation re-established a fragmented second-tier LPA administration based on *rayons*, and increased again the number of first-tier LPAs to 971 units, including 26 in the Autonomous Territorial Unit of Gagauzia (ATUG) and 70 localities in the breakaway Transnistrian region. Returning to *rayon* administration meant returning to a number of first-tier LPAs almost as in 1998, and therefore to the situation before the territorial and administrative reform. Second-tier LPA boundaries also changed, but the lower number of *rayons* was the consequence of the creation of the ATUG (which includes three former *rayons*, currently named *dolai*).

Changes in the administrative-territorial structure involved the creation of an additional institutional level – eight territorial offices of the State Chancellery. The main purpose of the territorial offices was to ensure the management of decentralized services, together with the ministries, which held the status of founders of decentralized regional services. This approach led to increased costs of providing services, which were accessible mainly in some of the cities which were also a *rayon* residence. First-tier LPAs were not yet able to provide most of the services to the population. The territorial offices of the State Chancellery were subsequently

⁹ Ion Beschieru and others, 'Studiu privind scenariile de reformă administrativ-teritorială' (publisher 2018) <https://cancelaria.gov.md/sites/default/files/studiul_privind_scenariile_de_reforma_administrativ-teritoriala_elaborat_in_decembrie_2018.pdf>.

reformed and transferred to the management of the former Ministry of Local Public Administration. In 2009, the territorial offices were transferred back to the State Chancellery.

Since 2009, administrative decentralization has been managed in the framework of the National Decentralization Strategy for the period 2012-2015, latter extended until 2018. This document aimed at transformation in a few areas, covering decentralization of services and skills; financial decentralization; patrimony decentralization and local development; administrative capacity of LPA; democracy, ethics, human rights, and gender equality.

According to the evaluation Report published in 2018 on the progress in the implementation of the strategy, '[t]he main policy documents and commitments in the field of decentralization and local self-government have expired and remain largely unimplemented.'¹⁰ Main achievement of the strategy is a progress in the local finances domain with the amendment of the Law no 397 on Local Public Finances that has introduced the general and special purpose transfers for the LPAs and subsequently the fiscal capacity principle for the distribution of the general purpose transfers.¹¹

Currently, the administrative and territorial organization of Moldova, apart from the Autonomous Territorial Unit of Gagauzia (ATUG), is based on two levels: villages (communes), sectors (of the Chisinau municipality) and cities (municipalities) that constitute the first-tier local public authorities (LPAs) and *rayons*, Chisinau and Balti municipalities that constitute the second-tier local governments. Urban localities are classified on four ranks according to a list of indicators that describe their level of social and economic development. From the total number of localities, 66 are urban, including 53 cities and 13 municipalities and 832 are rural. It is also important to mention that 597 localities, with very small population, do not have their own administration as they are part of a bigger administrative entity.

Territorial and administrative reform remains a key priority of the government in Moldova, and therefore is a sensitive subject in Moldovan politics. The government views the territorial and administrative fragmentation as one of the key challenges that needs to be addressed in order to strengthen local governments, reduce territorial disparities and improve service delivery.

Indeed, there are significant disparities across the spectrum of urban and rural first-tier LPAs in Moldova. Currently, 30 per cent of first-tier LPAs have less than 1,500 inhabitants, although, according to the legal provisions, for the formation of an administrative-territorial unit the number of population must be at least 1,500 inhabitants. At the same time, about 89 per cent of first-tier LPAs has a population of less than 5,000 inhabitants. In accordance with the legal provisions, administrative capacity is defined as adequate for an LPA if its administrative

¹⁰ 'Local Democracy Situation and the Degree of Implementation of Decentralization Policy Documents in the Field of Decentralization in the Republic of Moldova' (monitoring report, CALM/IDIS Viitorul 2018) <http://www.viitorul.org/files/Local%20Democracy%20Monitoring%20Report_Moldova.pdf>.

¹¹ 'Implementarea Strategiei naționale de descentralizare, discutată în cadrul Comisiei administrație publică' (*interlic*, 15 November 2017) <<http://www.interlic.md/2017-11-15/implementarea-strategiei-natzionale-de-descentralizare-discutata-in-cadrul-comisiei-administra-ie-pu-51458.html>>.

expenses do not exceed 30 per cent of the total amount of its own revenues. An analysis of the financial reports for 2017 reveal that not even one first-tier LPA met this legal criterion. On average, the administrative costs of first-tier LPAs are about 2 times higher than their own revenues. Moreover, only about 89 first-tier LPAs can cover their administrative expenses with their own revenues. The administrative expenditures in per capita terms in smaller first-tier LPAs (less than 1,500 inhabitants) are almost twice the national average. In larger first-tier LPAs (more than 5,000 inhabitants), administrative expenditures are 2.5 times smaller than in those LPAs with less than 1,500 inhabitants.

Along with administrative capacity, fiscal capacity per capita approximates the level of economic development of an LPA, being defined as the ratio between the amounts of income collected from Personal Income Tax (PIT), related to the number of inhabitants. Based on the data for 2017, only about 12 per cent of first-tier LPAs has a higher fiscal capacity per inhabitant than the national average (lei 697.14).

The share of capital investments in the total expenditures of first-tier LPAs is limited, being largely financed from special purpose transfers of the state budget, investment funds managed at the national level (energy efficiency fund, the ecological fund, the regional development fund, the social investment fund, etc.), as well as from external grants. The distribution of the funds allocated for capital investments is made in a highly non-transparent manner as there are no formula or any transparent rules or formulas governing the allocation. As a result, these allocations are considered as highly politicized. Also, there is no representation of the LPAs in the management of the investment funds created at the national level.¹²

It has to be mentioned that the situation regarding the provision of two essential local public services, the supply of drinking water and the collection, transport and storage of household waste, is very problematic. According to official statistics, in 2017 only 54.4 per cent of the country's population benefited from drinking water supply services. Also, the analysis in territorial profile shows the existence of large areas in the north, center and southeast of the Republic where less than 20 per cent of the population has access to the public drinking water supply system. In 2017, only 23.1 per cent of the total population had access to sewerage services, with a major difference between urban and rural areas, of 50.6 per cent and only 2.3 per cent, respectively.

Regarding the collection, transport and storage of household waste, according to the National Bureau of Statistics, in 2017, only 30.9 per cent of the population is served by sanitation services, the degree of coverage in urban areas being 64.1 per cent and only 6.0 per cent in rural areas. These figures are reinforced by the audit of the Court of Accounts carried out in

¹² Ion Meleştean, 'Clientelismul politic în alocarea resurselor publice din Bugetul de Stat către autoritățile publice locale' (Expert Grup 2018).

2017,¹³ which shows that 723 localities do not have access to public drinking water supply system and 1,378 localities, out of 1,521 in total do not benefit from sanitation services.

Nonetheless, there is little political or social consensus in Moldova related to the territorial and administrative reform. Voluntary amalgamation is a rather new concept in Moldova. While this form of bottom-up territorial and administrative reform has a high potential for success, still it lacks the development of a clear set of incentives for local communities and the necessary institutional framework.

Several analyses show that the lack of financial and administrative capacity of first-tier LPAs to provide a minimum amount of public services for the population remains a key challenge. From this perspective, the amalgamation of first-tier LPAs through a territorial and administrative reform is the major solution discussed and proposed by the central government. However, in Moldova there is little political or social consensus related to the administrative-territorial reform that would (or should in theory) lead to an improvement in the provision to the population of cost efficient and high quality public services. The issue of the identification of a proper balance between owned competencies and capacities to perform the mandatory functions still did not find a widely supported solution. The approaches to the resolution of these problems range between significant reductions of the administrative costs of the LPAs with subsequent risks related to limitation in the access of the population to the public services and centralization to the higher administrative level of the LPAs' competences.

Territorial reform against the background of high political instability and polarization raises significant concerns for local democracy and autonomy. Secondly, there are no sustainable grounds to believe that the administrative-territorial reform will bring any economies of scale. Even if the average size of Moldovan municipalities is increased, this will not necessarily prove to be more efficient and effective. Currently, there are towns with significantly higher population compared to small rural communities that are less efficient and there are many small municipalities with fairly high performance in the delivery of public services.

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¹³ Court of Accounts, 'Eficiența gestiunii economico-financiare și administrării patrimoniului de către întreprinderile care prestează servicii de aprovizionare cu apă a populației' (2017).

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